

Long-Term Impact of a Medical School Course on the Intersection of Art and Medical History

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Supplementary Materials

Course Description:

Below are descriptions of three of the sessions co-taught by B.G.C and B.S.C. Videos of three webinars that were developed for the Guggenheim Museum (Picturing Pandemic Diseases and Reading and Misreading Faces), and Stony Brook University (The Vaccine Wars) can be viewed at:

Picturing Pandemic Diseases: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E_noW0TBWmQ

Reading and Misreading Faces:

https://www.google.com/search?q=youtube+coller+reading+and+misreading&ei=ZNM1ZM_WEt_gptQP05yy4A4&ved=0ahUKEwjPmNWG5aL-AhVfkiKEHSOOD0wQ4dUDCBA&uact=5&oq=youtube+coller+reading+and+misreading&gs_lcp=Cgxn3Mtd2l6LXNlcnAQAzIFCCEQoAEyBQqhEKABOhYILhCDARDHARCxAXDRAXCKBRBD EOoEOhEILhCABBCxAXCDARDHARDRAzoLCC4QgAQQsQMqgwE6CwgAEIAEELEDEIMBOg0IABCKBRCxAXCDARBDOggILhCABBCxAZoICAAQgAQQsQM6IQguEIMBEMcBELEDENED EIoFEEMQ6gQQ3AQQ3gQQ4AQYAToWCC4QigUQsQMqgwEQxwEQ0QMqQxDqBDoKCAA QigUQsQMqQzoKCC4QigUQsQMqQzoHCAAQigUQzoKCC4QigUQ1AIQQzohCC4QigUQs QMqgwEQxwEQ0QMqQxDqBBDcBBDcBBDgBBgBOgUIABCABDoHCAAQgAQQCjoNCAAQ gAQQsQMqgwEQCjoICAAQigUQqQI6DggAEIoFELEDEIMBEJECOgoIABCABBCxAXAKOgUIL hCABDoGCAAQFhAeOggIABCKBRCGAzoHCAAQDRCADDoGCAAQHhANOGgIABAIEB4QDT oHCCEQoAEQCjoFCCEQgwI6CAghEBYQHhAdSgQIQRgAUABYoThgkkRoAHAAeACAAYcBi AGuGpIBBTI3LjEwmAEAoAEBwAEB2gEGCAEQARgU&scient=gws-wiz-serp#fpstate=ive&vld=cid:43d82c43,vid:TPpNSr8Xpww

The Vaccine Wars: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IRI5-C-4Vdw>

Observation in Medicine and Art: This topic introduces the concept that careful observation is crucial to both art and medicine. The Edwin Smith Papyrus of c.1600 BCE illustrates to modern students the power of fastidious observation alone, without any stethoscopes, ophthalmoscopes, laboratory tests, or imaging technology to provide important medical information.¹ This remarkable Egyptian medical manual, artistically calligraphed in hieratic, the cursive form of hieroglyphics used for priestly writing, is thought to be a copy of an older text from c.1800-1900 BCE. It describes recommendations for analyzing and treating 48 different types of wounds from the top of the head to the torso. Each of the medical cases is given a title, most of which are written in red ink, followed by a detailed analysis of the patient's

symptoms. Each case concludes with a recommendation to the physician as to whether he should announce that the problem is “an ailment I will handle, an ailment I will fight with, or an ailment for which nothing is done.” The careful observation and the wealth of medical experience embodied in this work are best illustrated by the two quotes that follow.

“One who has a wound in his neck, which has penetrated to the bone and violated a vertebra of his neck, and who suffers from stiffness in his neck: an ailment I will fight with.”

“One who has a dislocation in a vertebra of his neck, who is unaware of his legs and his arm, and whose urine is inert [i.e., the patient is incontinent]: an ailment for which nothing is done.”

It is sobering to realize that modern Western medicine does not begin until about 3500 years after the writing of the Edwin Smith Papyrus, when 16th century Renaissance anatomists used their extraordinary powers of observation to serve both artistic and medical purposes. Thus, art and modern medicine started out united in the works of Leonardo da Vinci and soon thereafter Andreas Vesalius of Brussels, the great Flemish anatomist. Leonardo was himself both the medical scientist and artist, performing autopsies to identify the cause of death, and conducting physiology experiments using his skills in casting and glass blowing to create a model of the aortic valve that led him to propose that the eddies produced during systole would close the valve in diastole. Vesalius worked closely with his Titian-trained, Flemish artist colleague, Jan Stephen van Kalleer, and/or with other artists in Titian’s studio, to produce the iconic woodcuts for his most important work, *De Humani Corporis Fabrica* (On the Fabric of the Human Body). Based on his masterly dissections of human cadavers, Vesalius provided new anatomic insights that selectively challenged some of the teachings of Galen, which had dominated medical thinking in the Western world for 1,500 years. Since in our current age we take for granted the central importance of direct, empiric observation, the historical importance of these works requires an understanding that the word “empiric” at that time was a term of disdain used to describe a medical quack who would dare to rely on observations rather than the accepted theories rooted in the Galenic tradition. Consequently, publishing personal observations that challenged Galenic dogma required courage.

Observation was not limited, however, to improving anatomic precision. In fact, it could also be used to infer dynamic bodily processes. This is most notably demonstrated by Harvey’s brilliantly accurate description of the circulation of the blood in *De Motu Cordis* (1628) based on his elegant experiments in which he observed the direction of blood flow in the veins in the forearm under a variety of circumstances. The iconic images of Harvey’s experiments are classics of both medical knowledge and art.

Careful observation alone, when coupled with insightful reasoning, is even sufficient to profoundly alter the entire course of scientific and medical thought, as witnessed by Darwin’s development of the theory of evolution based on his observations of variations among species. Armed with little more than a simple magnifying glass, he was able to combine his precise measurements of animals with the power of his extraordinary scientific inductive reasoning to set forth the theory of evolution, the foundation of modern biology. The intensity of Darwin’s observation was itself remarkable in many ways. A compulsive beetle collector starting in his youth, he later spent eight years analyzing and categorizing different types of barnacles, resulting

in several monographs between 1851-4 that helped to secure his reputation for scientific rigor even before the publication of the Origin of Species in 1859.

Observational science in medicine perhaps reached its pinnacle, perhaps in the studies and teachings of Sir William Osler, who integrated intense and systemized bedside observation with equally intense and systematized anatomic observations at autopsy, both grossly and at the microscopic level. The clinico-pathological correlations that emerged formed the foundation of modern medicine at the beginning of the twentieth century. Osler was also the consummate educator. We show the class a series of photographs reprinted in *William Osler, A Life in Medicine* by Michael Bliss that captures him systematically observing and examining patients at the bedside and in a demonstration classroom, surrounded in the latter by students equally intensely observing the patient. In one of the photographs, Osler's contemplative pose as he sits by the bedside is similar to that of Rodin's *The Thinker*. Juxtaposing them in a single slide reinforces the intensity of Osler's concentration and the importance of observing a person's body language in understanding a person's state of mind; it also places him in a classical context. Osler wrote explicitly about the importance of observation in Medicine: "Medicine is learned by the bedside and not in the classroom. Let not your conception of manifestations of disease come from work heard in the lecture room or read from the book: see and then research, compare and control. But see first." "The whole art of medicine is in observation." "To make perfect that most difficult of all arts, the art of observation...."

The photograph of Osler at the bedside of a patient, surrounded by his students, also suggests comparison with a nineteenth century work of art. The 1879 painting by Mary Cassatt, *At the Opera*, similarly captures a layering of simultaneous acts of observation and being observed. In the photograph Osler fixes his attention on the patient while his students variably gaze at the patient or the Professor. Thus, Osler is both the intense observer and the intensely observed. In Cassatt's work, the attractive young opera-lover, and most of the rest of the audience, focus their attention on the stage. The notable exception is the man who conspicuously uses his opera glasses to better see the young woman. Although they both use opera glasses to enhance vision, the directional disparity of their gazes sets up tension and tells a story of romantic attraction across a public space. Darwin might well appreciate how Cassatt painted an image of the process of mate selection based on physical attractiveness, made possible by intense observation.

That great observers in medical history had the ability to see things others couldn't, highlights the discipline and training required to conduct careful observation. It also provides an opportunity to discuss with the class participants why careful observation may seem to be simple, but in fact, is difficult, especially in the present era. First and foremost is the time required, since the pressures of the modern age leave little time for prolonged, uninterrupted observation. Second is the unifocal intensity required at a time when nearly perpetual multitasking is the norm. Third is the need to consciously overcome the automatic and unconscious "filling in" that our brains have been conditioned to provide when making sense of our visual inputs so as to speed up the process of image recognition with the least amount of information. Finally, looking at patients for medical purposes has to overcome other obstacles, including the social conventions that make us and those we are observing uncomfortable if we stare at them (or even a part of them) for a prolonged period of time. In academic settings, as with Osler, there often is the added complexity of students and trainees observing the observing physician/teacher, who may simultaneously feel the pressure of being both the observer and the one being observed.

As an example of observation in art, we introduce the familiar artistic subject, the landscape, which has nearly infinite variations. We begin with a humorous artistic experiment with landscape motifs conducted by the artist duo known as Komar and Melamid entitled *Most Wanted Painting*. Employing a “scientific” approach to their art, Komar and Melamid surveyed 1,001 people in the United States about what they liked to see in paintings. Their responses revealed that a majority of Americans liked landscapes, the color blue, animals, water, and historic personages. They then used this information to create a painting designed to please most American viewers. It is an outdoor setting with a lake and blue sky, and containing images of two deer and George Washington, who stands by the shore. The resulting formulaic and banal painting highlights the difference between real artistic creativity and pandering to public consensus.

This painting is then contrasted with the extraordinarily beautiful landscape by the French artist, Gustave Caillebotte entitled *Yerres, L'effet de Pluie*. In the students' discussion of their initial reactions to the painting, they commonly identify several unusual features: the vertical format; the absence of people and animals; three distinctly divided areas representing the ground, the Yerres river, and trees against a gray sky; the subtle tilt of perspective upward toward the viewer; the large percentage of the picture devoted to patterns created when rain drops land on water; and the unusual cropping of the edges of the composition, which limits the viewer's ability to see the periphery. These distinctive artistic choices are then placed in a historical and art historical context by showing their similarity to qualities evident in the works of several Japanese printmakers in the nineteenth century. The connection is supported by historical evidence since many artists in Caillebotte's circle in Paris discovered Japanese woodcut prints in the 1860s and 1870s and adapted their eccentric vantage points, flattened and bold areas of color, and sharply-cropped edges into their own work. Examples of Japanese prints of rainy landscapes such as *Sudden Shower over Shin-Ōhashi Bridge and Atake* by Ando Hiroshige reveal strong compositional similarities. Thus, careful observation of how this painting differed from expectations of a more typical and expected organization of space, and the common natural elements (land, water, trees, sky) illuminate the history and context of this particular work.

To contrast the example of observation in art with observation in medicine, we next discuss the analysis of a blood smear, which also requires careful, systematic observation and active mental engagement. The systematic review of a blood smear incorporates all of the key elements of the scientific method, including observation, hypothesis development, and hypothesis testing. It also includes hypothesis modification or rejection, when appropriate, followed by new hypothesis development. For example, if the blood platelets are analyzed first, and the number observed is estimated to be lower than normal, one can generate a differential diagnosis of the causes of thrombocytopenia. Since the blood smear is a very rich source of data, it is possible to begin narrowing down the differential diagnosis by further evaluation of the same blood smear. As observations are made about the other cells, diagnoses become either more or less likely, until there is no more information to be gleaned. Thus, in the case of thrombocytopenia due to thrombotic thrombocytopenia purpura (TTP), one would expect to observe red blood cell fragmentation, whereas in immune thrombocytopenic purpura (ITP), one would typically expect the red cells to have normal morphology. In the case of aplastic anemia, one would expect to observe a decrease in the white blood cell count in addition to a low platelet count, and normal red cell morphology. When all of the information contained on the blood smear has been obtained and combined with the patient's clinical history, physical findings, and laboratory data, one can

construct the most likely provisional diagnosis or diagnoses as a prelude to obtaining additional data to try to confirm the diagnosis.

Near the end of each class, the students are asked a question to stimulate discussion. For this session it is to compare careful observation in art and medicine and to highlight both the similarities and differences. Both require intense concentration and benefit greatly from the viewer having both extensive experience and a robust store of knowledge so as to be able to judge when something is truly original (in art) or atypical or abnormal (in medicine). In addition, a full understanding requires context. In the case of art, this includes an appreciation of the work's place in the artist's career and in the history of art, including the dominant social, political, and economic conditions that influenced people when and where the work was made. In the case of medicine, it is the patient's medical history, current signs and symptoms, and laboratory data that provide the context, along with the dominant views about the pathophysiology of disease. The profound difference, of course, is that directly observing patients who are vitally concerned about their health, variably concerned about their appearance and modesty, and constantly searching the physician's eyes for hope and any possible clue about their diagnosis and prognosis, imposes constraints that don't exist when contemplating an inanimate work of art. Moreover, as with Osler, in an academic setting, the attending physician is not only the observer, but also the observed when students and trainees are present. Having to function simultaneously as physician and role model in this setting can be particularly stressful. This discussion often raises the question as to whether one of the reasons so many people, including physicians, enjoy viewing works of art is that they are free to observe for as long as they like, and as intently as they like, without fear of transgressing a social norm. To conclude, the sculptures of the artist Duane Hanson are used to highlight this point because they depict everyday people in the midst of typical activities with such remarkable realism that they simultaneously elicit fascination with, and wonder at, how the artist achieves such verisimilitude and an uneasy sense of transgressing a social norm by staring at the "person" even though it is an inanimate object.

Skin Deep: Dermatology in Art: This session combines observation and discussion and adds student participation in the form of making art related to medicine. It provides both a welcome change to the standard tutorial format and an opportunity for social bonding among the students. An artist, Hope Grayson, serves as a guest co-leader of this session.

Jacques Louis David's painting, *The Death of Marat or Last Breath of Marat* serves to introduce a discussion centered on diseases of the skin. It is a stark and powerful portrait of the political writer and activist of the French Revolution, Jean-Paul Marat. He was murdered with a kitchen knife by Charlotte Corday, a young girl who opposed Marat's political views. In an extraordinary melding of narrative skill, political acumen, classical simplicity, and religious references, David depicted Marat just after his death. It was well-known during Marat's life that he suffered from an undiagnosed skin ailment and that he received a measure of relief by soaking in a bathtub. As a result, he not only carried out his work on a board spread over the tub, but also received visitors in this unusual setting. In the painting, David included the mundane tools of the writer's profession – pen, inkwell, and paper – near the lifeless body of Marat, but elevated the death scene with compositional allusions to Christ after his crucifixion. This is evident by comparing Marat's pose to that of Christ in the *Pieta* by David's student, Anne-Louis Girardot. In this way, David transforms Marat into a saintly, political martyr intended to both inspire veneration and rally the French public. After reading contemporary descriptions of Marat's skin symptoms and a summary of his life circumstances, the class discusses the many possible diagnoses that

have been suggested, including atopic eczema, seborrheic dermatitis, diabetic candidiasis, scabies, syphilis, histiocytosis, and dermatitis herpetiformis.²⁻⁴

A more modern work by the artist Lucio Fontana, *Spatial Concept* provides a more open-ended connection to dermatology. In this work, as in many of his other works, the artist slices his monochrome canvas, producing a large vertical slit that pierces the surface. The students quickly recognize the similarities between the slits in the canvas and wounds that destroy the integrity of the surface of skin. After learning that the artist was wounded in World War I, the students are better able to place the work in context of the artist's life, and to discuss its implications for understanding wounds, healing, and scarring, as well as cutting as a violating, yet essential, part of surgery.

The session culminates in a discussion of a provocative wall assemblage by the Korean-American artist Byron Kim, entitled *Synecdoche*. The version of the painting that we show consists of 275 9.8 x 7.9 inch squares evenly arranged in eleven rows of twenty five. Each square is painted a solid shade that ranges from beiges to dark brown; no two squares are the same shade. When the students first see an image of this work, they usually comment that it looks like a "catalogue of store paint samples." They are then told that paint in each square was mixed to match the color of the skin on the forearms of the artist's family members, friends, and selected strangers. The meaning of the title, *Synecdoche*, a part that stands for the whole, leads to the interpretation that each square stands for a person, and the work can be seen as a group portrait of the 275 people represented.

To engage the students more actively in this session, they are then given a paintbrush, a plastic plate to act as a mixing palette, two square pieces of paper, and a plastic cup with water. Tubes of acrylic paint in various colors are placed in the center of the table, including "flesh," and various shades of peach, beige, red, yellow, purple, and brown. Each student then spends the next ten minutes trying to emulate Bryon Kim by mixing the paints to achieve the shade that best matches the skin his or her own forearm. They then paint both squares of paper that color. One square is collected and the other is used as the background on which they copy an image of one or more skin disorders (e.g., poison ivy, chicken pox, keloid scar, and Lyme disease) selected from a collection of photographs of patients. This requires intense observation and results in a better appreciation of how skin color can affect the appearance of different lesions.

While the students work on the second square, the collected colored squares are arranged on a large foam core rectangle to recreate the class's version of Byron Kim's *Synecdoche*. The grid comprised of the individual squares with the students' own skin tones constitutes an abstract "class portrait"—individuals of different colors who make up a community. The students leave with enhanced appreciation of "synecdoche," variations in skin tones, the importance and power of careful observation and the satisfaction of creating their own work of art.

The Gross Clinic and the Ascendancy of American Science and Medicine in the 19th Century: The emergence of American scientific and medical leadership in the nineteenth century is highlighted by several works of art, including, Charles Wilson Peale's 1822 painting, *The Artist in His Museum*, Thomas Eakins's two famous paintings of 1875 and 1889, *The Clinic of Dr. Gross* and *The Agnew Clinic*, and the 1906 painting, *The Four Doctors* by John Singer Sargent.

Peale's painting self-confidently trumpets the success of both American natural history and art since Peale himself is both a discoverer and the artist. He dominates the painting, inviting the viewer to enter his museum of extraordinary specimens, which was originally housed adjacent

to Philadelphia's Independence Hall and opened in 1786. It was the first public natural history museum in the U.S. and the first to use Linnaean taxonomy. The historical context is crucial since it preceded the great natural history museums that opened to the public in the nineteenth century, including the Academy of Natural Science of Philadelphia in 1828, the American Museum of Natural History in New York in 1869, and the forerunner of the Field Museum in Chicago in 1893. These institutions reflected a new national commitment to science education as American naturalists, like Peale, were making great discoveries, proudly putting them on display, and infusing the entire enterprise with a sense of public-minded spirit and pride.

Because it is partially hidden, it takes some time for the viewer to identify the star of Peale's collection, a mastodon skeleton. Once its enormous scale is appreciated, however, one understands why the woman viewing it in the background gestures in a manner that indicates profound amazement and surprise, bordering on shock. In sharp contrast, the young boy nearby seems to be calmly viewing the skeleton while the male adult next to him, presumably his father, appears to be teaching him. The differences in the responses by the woman and the boy and man reflect gender-specific stereotypes of the time.

Peale contributed directly to natural history discoveries as documented in his earlier painting, *Exhuming the First American Mastodon* (1802), which graphically depicts his 1801 excavation in Montgomery, New York. Peale is shown surrounded by members of his large family as he actively directs a large group of men who are working in a water-filled pit to recover the bones. A large wheel powered by human labor to remove the water occupies a prominent place in the painting, reinforcing both the limitations and ingenuity that characterized American life prior to the availability of engines powered by steam, gasoline, or electricity. Peale's discovery had deeper implications since the existence of mastodons in the U.S. provided valuable support for Thomas Jefferson's views in his dispute with the Comte de Buffon about whether Europe or the Americas contained superior biologic species.⁵ In fact, Jefferson offered U.S. Army and Navy assistance to Peale for his 1801 excavation. The discovery also was prime evidence for species extinction, an idea that was at odds with biblical orthodoxy.

Thomas Eakins's paintings from the late nineteenth century are discussed next, but, as a prelude, we review Rembrandt's 1632 iconic medical work, the *Anatomy Lesson of Professor Nicolaes Tulp*, commonly known as Dr. Tulp's Anatomy Lesson.⁶ This group portrait of identifiable persons, whose names are on the list held by the figure in the back, pays tribute to Dr. Tulp's stature and his skills in dissecting cadavers. Although much has been written and discussed about this painting from an art historical perspective, from a medical historical standpoint, two points bear emphasis. The first is that Dr. Tulp is not treating a patient; rather, he is using a dead person to teach anatomy. Public dissections were only permitted by the governmental authorities once a year, with the stipulation that they had to be performed on executed prisoners. Thus, it was a matter of public record that the cadaver depicted in the painting was a criminal executed on January 16, 1632. Second, cast in shadows in the lower right-hand corner of the painting is a large opened book. Although lacking positive identification, many authorities believe this book to be Vesalius's, *De Humani Corporis Fabrica* discussed previously. This identification gains support from noting that Vesalius's own self portrait in the *Fabrica* shows him dissecting the arm of a cadaver in which he demonstrates the same muscles that Dr. Tulp demonstrates in his anatomy lesson. Rembrandt may thus be honoring Dr. Tulp as a modern day successor to Vesalius. Rembrandt improves on the static dissection that Vesalius depicted in the *Fabrica*, however, by ingeniously suggesting motion in his painting. He does this by having some of the observers in

the painting look at the dissected arm and others look at Dr. Tulp's unexpectedly bent left hand, which has already adopted the position that the cadaver's hand is about to adopt when Dr. Tulp moves the muscle (flexor digitorum superficialis) that he holds in the clamp.⁷

Eakin's 1875 painting of Dr. Gross of Jefferson Medical College in Philadelphia, *The Clinic of Dr. Gross*, better known as *The Gross Clinic*, is the perfect combination of 19th century heroic painting and medical history. It provides a dramatic demonstration of the ascent of American medicine in the latter half of the century, asserting its emerging role at the international level. Eakins, who studied anatomy in Philadelphia and France, painted the portrait without a commission, with the goal of having it shown at the 1876 U.S. Centennial Exhibition in Philadelphia. The Centennial Exhibition was to be a showcase for America's achievements during its first one hundred years, and Eakins was particularly interested in countering the demeaning attitude of English and European physicians toward American Medicine. Eakins was, however, a controversial figure in Philadelphia, in part, because of his insistence on examining the nude to learn human anatomy. *The Gross Clinic* was rejected from the art section of the Centennial, but was displayed in the Hospital Pavilion. Even in that context, however, it was severely criticized by some reviewers because of the blood on the scalpel and on Dr. Gross's hand. Thus, what is now considered a masterpiece combining the complex orchestration of numerous figures and the dramatic representation of a revered physician educator conducting a novel surgical technique while instructing a group of students, received very mixed reactions from both the public and critics when first exhibited.

Eakins greatly admired Dr. Gross, in part because he was able to become one of the country's most prominent surgeons and president of the American Medical Association despite coming from a humble background. Thus, Gross's career epitomized America as a country with social mobility and merit-based recognition. Despite what may appear to the modern viewer to be radical surgery, in fact, the painting depicts Dr. Gross performing a limb-sparing operation that he perfected for treating osteomyelitis of the femur, reinforcing the advanced state of American surgery. In addition, the patient is enjoying the benefit of surgical anesthesia, which was first developed in the U.S. using ether in the 1840s.

Eakins chose not to depict Dr. Gross in the act of performing the surgery directly on the body, but rather in the act of teaching, emphasizing his personal commitment to education and the increasing sophistication of American medical education. The scribe in the painting is the clinic clerk Dr. Franklin West, who is taking notes on Dr. Gross's surgery; these will later be published in journals and/or in one of the many books that Gross wrote. Thus, in sharp contrast to Rembrandt's portrait of Dr. Tulp's anatomy lesson, Dr. Gross is not following the guideposts already laid out in a textbook, but rather he is breaking new ground with innovative surgery, and his discoveries will be published in professional journals and books that will be disseminated near and far so that others can benefit from his findings.

There are many other facets of *The Gross Clinic* that provide themes for discussion with the medical students and they are given the opportunity to discover them in teams through close observation. Since high intensity electric lights had not yet been invented in 1875, surgery was limited to only those times of day when sunlight would stream through the oculus in the dome of the surgical amphitheater. The female figure to the left of Dr. Gross, who covers her eyes in apparent anguish, is commonly identified as the patient's mother, raising questions about the reported practice at that time of having a family member present at operations on charity patients. Additional questions naturally arise about the informed consent procedures, payment for services,

and the socioeconomic status of the patient. Perhaps the most striking feature of the painting to modern viewers, but not viewers at the time of the painting, is Dr. Gross's street clothing and lack of surgical gloves or mask. Despite the work of Holmes, Semmelweis, Pasteur, and Lister, Dr. Gross had not adopted antisepsis in his surgical practice. By such detailed analysis, the students come to appreciate the treasure trove of information that can be derived from carefully observing and analyzing a single painting.

The Agnew Clinic, painted by Eakins 14 years later, provides multiple vivid contrasts to The Gross Clinic, and graphically demonstrates the rapid evolution of American surgical practice during this period. The painting was done on commission by the University of Pennsylvania Medical School graduating class to honor Dr. Agnew, who was a member of a socially prominent Philadelphia family; Dr. Agnew is dressed in a white surgical gown and wears surgical gloves (but no mask); the amphitheater is bathed in electric lighting; a nurse is a prominent member of the surgical team; and the patient who is undergoing a mastectomy, is partially covered with sterile drapes. Contemporaneous accounts of mastectomies performed at that time indicate that only the breast being operated on would ordinarily be exposed in the operating field, and so it may well be that Eakins made the decision to uncharacteristically deviate from depicting the operation accurately for artistic or other reasons. In further sharp contrast to *The Gross Clinic*, remarkably little blood is visible in The Agnew Clinic. Both paintings, however, focus on the surgeon as teacher, with students displaying variably intense interest and concentration. Noting the students in the gallery in the painting who appear to be dozing during the surgery provides a stimulus for the modern-day students to discuss their own student experiences. Some things may be universal and timeless!

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